

CAR-T Therapy and CRISPR/Cas9 in Cancer Treatment

Ememobong Eka

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Author Note

Ememobong Eka <https://orcid.org/0009-0000-6997-0329>

Independent researcher with no formal affiliation.

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Correspondence should be addressed to me, Ememobong Eka.

Email: em9017699@gmail.com

Abstract

CAR-T and CRISPR/Cas9 are two biotechnologies that have exhibited promising results in the field of cancer treatment. They are also constantly remarked for their consistent progress in clinical and preclinical trials alike. CAR-T Therapy is a type of immunotherapy and it redirects T cells to target cancer cells. Additionally, CRISPR/Cas9 Gene Editing is a gene editing tool that enhances the capabilities of CAR-T Therapy. Individually, they have shown proficient abilities in defense against cancer. However, they have both experienced limitations in its ability to tackle many types of cancers beyond blood cancers. Particularly, they are in need of progress towards their effect against solid malignancies. Although they seem to be a reliable option for cancer treatment even on their own, they seem to fall short when it comes to a multitude of different cancers. However, together they can form a powerful treatment against other types of cancers beyond blood cancers including solid malignancies.

Keywords: CAR-T, CRISPR-based systems, Cancer, Synthetic Biology

CAR-T Therapy and CRISPR/Cas9 in Cancer Treatment

CAR-T Therapy and CRISPR/Cas9 Gene editing are promising forms of cancer treatment and biotechnologies, and are noted for their progress in preclinical and clinical trials. These technologies create the basis for further advancement of cancer treatment. CAR-T Therapy is a form of immunotherapy that redirects T cells to target cancer cells, CRISPR/Cas9 Gene Editing is a gene editing tool that enhances the capabilities of CAR-T Therapy. Thus, together they can form a powerful treatment against other types of cancers beyond blood cancers including solid malignancies.

Along with recent progress in both biotechnologies, they show promise for great change in the field of cancer treatment. Individually, they have shown proficient abilities in defense against cancer. For CAR-T Therapy, so far it has been proven effective against leukemia, lymphoma, and myeloma and approved as a cancer treatment by the Food and Drug Administration (Young et al., 2023). In terms of its use for solid malignancies, it has been less effective than in blood cancers. In fact, there are barriers in CAR-T Therapy that lead to inefficiency in solid tumours and reasons for this range from a lack of safe target antigens, poor CAR T cell trafficking, T cell dysfunction, and possibly a lack of t-cell fitness (Hull & Maher, 2021). A visualization of this biotechnology is presented in Figure 1. Although this yields minimal progress for solid malignancies, given its improved performance against certain hematological cancers, there can be hope for it to progress into solid malignancies in the near future. Likewise, CRISPR/Cas9 Gene Editing has impacted the way cancer is treated and is a somewhat reliable option for cancer treatment. It is more recent than CAR-T and is enhancing the potency of immune cells and “CRISPR–Cas9-mediated genome engineering holds immense promise to treat or even cure genetic disorders, including many forms of cancer” (Jiang &

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Doudna, 2017). Regarding recent results for it against solid tumors, in a similar way to CAR-T Therapy, CRISPR/Cas9 Gene Editing still has much advancements to undergo before it could tackle it adequately. A detailed visualization of this biotechnology is presented in Figure 2. Consequently, CRISPR/Cas9 Gene Editing is useful against certain types of hematological malignancies but it falls short for solid malignancies; however, with further trials it could reach a point where it can start to treat solid tumors. Despite these biotechnologies exhibiting great abilities and results, they require more advancements to supersede blood cancers and become applicable to many other types of cancers.

On the other hand, despite their potential for greatness for advancements in cancer treatments, they have their potential downfalls and limitations. Firstly, CAR-T poses a threat on healthy T-cells and can be a detriment to the human body. As researchers Young et al. (2023) have explained, there are side effects of CAR-T that needs to be addressed in relation to its effect on healthy immune cells; in fact, “CART Targeting T cell malignancies with CAR T cells would threaten the healthy T cell compartment as a consequence of shared target gene expression” (p. 4). Additionally, CAR-T has its limitations, especially pertaining to its effectiveness against solid malignancies; “Specific target antigens on solid tumors are more difficult to identify. Roughly 30 solid tumor antigens are being evaluated for CAR T-cell therapy” (Cartellieri et al., 2010). It is evident that despite the recent progress of CAR-T Therapy, they require more improvement to deal with their adverse effects, especially on cells and to be able to handle the complexities that come with solid tumors to effectively deal with them. Likewise, CRISPR/Cas9 Gene Editing have their shortcomings and fall short on a few critical areas for treating cancer. CRISPR/Cas9 Gene Editing are by no means perfect and have further technical issues to address. One of those problems involves off-target mutations and for them to function better “Reducing or avoiding

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any unwanted off-target mutations at sites with sequence homology to on-target sites is paramount for the effective use of CRISPR-mediated genome engineering in clinical applications” (Jiang & Doudna, 2017). Adding on, there is another issue that arises from the usage of CRISPR/Cas9 Gene Editing that pertains to off-target prediction and it is shown that “effective methods are now available that permit identification of off-target cleavage events, a major class of potential side effects seen in mammalian genome editing” (Vakulskas & Behlke, 2019). Moreover, in a similar way to CAR-T Therapy, CRISPR/Cas9 Gene Editing are inadequate against solid tumors and have made minimal advancements against solid tumors in recent clinical trials. Therefore, CRISPR/Cas9 Gene Editing is in need of advancements and solutions for it to reach its fullest capacity and treat more complex types of cancers and solid malignancies with lesser off-target effects and adversities. Consequently, CAR-T Therapy and CRISPR/Cas9 Gene Editing display sufficient capabilities for treating a multitude of cancers beyond blood cancers, however they have different problems to be solved concerning their adversities, off-target effects, and current ineffectiveness against solid malignancies.

Furthermore, the potential of CAR-T therapy and CRISPR/Cas9 is also shown when the two are combined. When combined, they can improve function, enhance effectiveness against solid malignancies, and promote better offense against other types of blood cancers beyond acute leukemia. In recent times, CRISPR/Cas9 is being utilized to enhance the existing capabilities of CAR-T and “the identification and CRISPR-Cas9 mediated knockout of genes that restrain tumor immunity has enabled the production of next-generation CAR T cells” (Young et al., 2023). It is clear that these biotechnologies not only are adequate on their own, but when combined, they can elicit groundbreaking results for cancer treatment.

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Overall, both biotechnologies are promising and have been proven to enhance the way cancer is treated. Although they have their individual limitations, together they can create a coherent treatment for a multitude of cancer types. As a result, they could be capable of handling the complexities that come with other types of cancers including solid tumors.

Figure 1

Illustration of the mechanisms of CAR-T

Note. This diagram was taken from the Corewell Health website, in which it shows the mechanisms involved in CAR-T.

Figure 2

Illustration of the mechanisms and function of CRISPR/Cas9

How does **CRISPR-Cas9** work?

- Adapted from defense mechanism against virus of bacteria
- Cas9 is an enzyme using guide RNA leading to cut target DNA sequence
- Desired genetic sequence could add in repairing system for customize DNA

Note. This diagram was taken from the LIVESCIENCE website in which it shows the mechanisms and functions involved in CRISPR/Cas9 systems.

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